

Normal Organic Salts of Tungsten

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Several normal organic salts of tungsten have been prepared by the action of tungsten (VI) chloride on mono- and dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids. The properties of the compounds have been studied and their structures discussed.

Fernandes (*Gazzetta*, 1923, 53, 514) prepared some heteropoly compounds of gallic acid with molybdic, tungstic, and uranic anhydrides. By polarimetric analysis and pH determinations, Raman and Vaishya (this *Journal*, 1934, 11, 179) observed complex formation between sodium tartrate and tungsten salts in the molecular proportions of 3:2 and 2:1 respectively. Sartori (*Gazzetta*, 1934 64, 17) studied the preparation of some tungstoquinates and molybdoquinates. Pan *et al.* (*Chemistry*, Taiwan, No. 2, pp. 17-25, 1954) studied the composition of the complexes formed between tungstate and organic acids by conductometric titration.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the formation of normal salts of tungsten with mono- and dicarboxylic acids, and hydroxy-acids and the properties of the compounds formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of Merck's or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality. Tungsten (VI) chloride was prepared as before (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 588). The organic solvents were dehydrated and redistilled.

Tungsten (VI) chloride in CCl_4 was mixed with an excess of the acid, suspended in CCl_4 . The mixture was slowly warmed at about 60° on an oil bath for nearly half an hour. The temperature of the bath was then slowly raised and finally the residue was heated at a temperature $10\text{--}15^\circ$ higher than the m.p. of the acid till the evolution of HCl (gas) had ceased, the reaction having been carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The product was washed well with ether or other organic solvents till free of acid and dried in vacuum.

A weighed quantity of the compound was digested with HNO_3 (conc.) for several hours on a water bath. It was evaporated to dryness, ignited, and weighed as WO_3 . The percentage of tungsten and empirical formula of the compound were calculated from the weight of WO_3 obtained. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by combustion method in four cases and in the rest the organic matter was found by difference. Products obtained are listed in Table I.

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, insoluble in CCl_4 , ether, and benzene, but sparingly soluble in ethanol. Tungsten laurate and tungsten myristate are, however, sparingly soluble in CCl_4 and in benzene. The compounds did not respond to tests for chlorine. These are very stable in dry atmosphere, hydrolyse slowly on boiling with water, and are decomposed by acids and alkalis.

DISCUSSION

One molecule of WCl_6 reacts with six molecules of a monocarboxylic acid and three molecules of a dicarboxylic acid, the reaction being more vigorous with the latter.

With the hydroxy-acids the reaction is vigorous and the hydrogen of the carboxyl and the hydroxyl groups is displaced. In all the cases the corresponding tungsten salts are formed.

Nitro-acids give similar results. In 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid both the carboxyl and the hydroxyl groups are affected as in hydroxy-acids.

The authors' sincere thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing the necessary facilities.

TABLE I

Acids.	Product.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Organic matter	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
A. Tungsten (VI) chloride with monocarboxylic acids. WCl_6 : acid = 1 : 6.						
1. Lauric	$[C_{18}(CH_2)_{16}COO]_6W$	Black	13.48	13.35	86.52 C: 62.13 H: 9.86	86.65 62.69 10.01
2. Myristic	$[C_{14}(CH_2)_{12}COO]_6W$	Greyish brown	11.63	11.90	88.37	88.10
3. Palmitic	$[C_{16}(CH_2)_{14}COO]_6W$	Dark brown	10.70	10.73	89.30	89.27
4. Stearic	$[C_{18}(CH_2)_{16}COO]_6W$	Brown	9.48	9.77	90.52	90.23
5. Benzoic	$[C_6H_5COO]_6W$	Greyish black	20.59	20.21	79.41	79.79
6. <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic	$[NO_2-C_6H_4COO]_6W$	Brown	15.86	15.59	84.14	84.41
7. " "	" "	Light brown	15.64	15.59	84.36	84.41
8. Crotonic	$[CH_3CH=CHCOO]_6W$	Brown	26.40	26.51	73.60	73.49
9. Cinnamic	$[C_6H_5CH=CHCOO]_6W$	Dark brown	17.21	17.26	82.79	82.74
B. Tungsten (VI) chloride with dicarboxylic acids. WCl_6 : acid = 1 : 3.						
10. Malonic	$[CH_2(COO)]_3W$	Light brown	37.16	37.54	62.84	62.46
11. Adipic	$[(CH_2)_4(COO)]_3W$	Black	29.48	29.86	70.52 C: 35.31 H: 3.736	70.14 35.09 3.896
12. Succinic	$\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2COO \\ \\ CH_2COO \end{array} \right]_3W$	Greyish brown	34.50	34.57	65.50	65.43
13. Camphoric	$[C_{10}H_{14}(COO)]_3W$	Brownish black	23.96	23.64	76.04	76.36
14. Phthalic	$[C_6H_4(COO)]_3W$	Dark brown	27.28	27.20	72.72	72.80
C. Tungsten (VI) chloride with hydroxy-acids.						
15. Salicylic	$\left[\begin{array}{c} O \\ \\ C_6H_4 \\ \\ COO \end{array} \right]_3W$	Brown	30.72	31.07	69.28 C: 42.19 H: 2.132	68.93 42.57 2.027
16. 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic	$\left[\begin{array}{c} O \\ \\ (NO_2)_2-C_6H_3 \\ \\ COO \end{array} \right]_3W$	Light brown	21.06	21.34	78.94	78.66
17. Malic	$[CH_2CHO(COO)]_3W$	Black	40.83	41.24	59.17 C: 21.01 H: 1.298	58.76 21.53 1.346

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Received October 11, 1960.